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Impact Of Artificial Intelligence Technology On Digital Management Of Educational Systems In Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study investigates the impact of Artificial Intelligence (AI) technology on the digital management of educational systems in Nigeria. The research aims to examine how AI tools are being utilized to improve administrative efficiency, data management, and educational delivery in secondary and tertiary institutions. The study adopts a descriptive survey research design using the random sampling technique to select 380 lecturers and students, from three public and two private universities in Delta State, Nigeria. Data were collected using structured questionnaires and analyzed using descriptive statistics and t-test statistics. Results indicate that a complex but progressively positive landscape exists for AI adoption in Nigerian educational institutions. While the use of specific AI tools in core academic functions such as grading, advising, and scheduling remains limited, AI is gradually making a notable impact in administrative areas. The study concludes that There is a growing recognition of AI's value in streamlining operations, however, widespread integration is still hindered by real and significant barriers that must be addressed for the full benefits of AI to be realized across the education sector in Nigeria. The study recommends the establishment of clear frameworks and guidelines to support the structured adoption and use of AI and Increased funding and investment for AI integration while addressing implementation barriers for sustainable AI adoption in the Nigerian education sector.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Technology, Digital Management, Educational Systems

INTRODUCTION

The rapid advancement of Artificial Intelligence (AI) has profoundly influenced numerous sectors of society, including healthcare, finance, agriculture and education. Within the educational mainstream, AI technologies are increasingly being incorporated into both administrative and instructional processes to improve efficiency, accuracy, and student responsiveness. According to Erbas and Maksuti (2024) AI presents tremendous possibilities and notable obstacles, while transforming teaching approaches, enriched learning encounters, and fundamentally altering the dynamics between technology and within the teaching and learning paradigm, as educational systems are globally adopting AI-driven solutions for a range of functions, such as analysis of test results, intelligent tutoring and automated grading.

The integration of AI into education is being approached through a variety of applications designed to support both instructional delivery and institutional management, as intelligent tutoring systems is being increasingly patronized, with the aim of providing personalized learning experiences by adapting content to individual student needs, while automated grading tools seek to streamline assessment processes and reduce administrative workload. Akgun and Greenhow, (2022) explained that the concept of AI is about the combination of applications of machine learning, deep learning, algorithm production, and natural

language processing that is beneficial for scholarly organizations and individuals, as it can increase efficiency, productivity, save time and effort, while improving overall performance (Ali, Abdelbaki, Shrestha, Elbasi, Alryalat, & Dwivedi, 2023; Flavian & Casalo, 2021). Additionally, AI is being utilized in analyzing large data for informed decision-making, monitor student progress, and optimize resource allocation. These applications reflect a broader trend toward data-driven practices in education, with the objective of improving educational outcomes and operational efficiency. However, the extent and effectiveness of AI adoption vary across regions and institutions, influenced by factors such as infrastructure, policy frameworks, and stakeholder engagement.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has emerged as a transformative force in education, with applications spanning from personalized learning and intelligent tutoring systems to administrative automation and decision support. Mureşan (2023) highlighted that the use of Artificial Intelligence continues to grow in the education sector. It is becoming increasingly clear to all that it offers many exciting possibilities for the learning outcomes of pupils/students. According to Erbas & Maksuti (2024) AI has rapidly become one of the most widely utilized technologies in modern history, integrated into billions of smartphones for various services, as these systems rely on network machine learning methods to perform a variety of classifications (Herman-Cappelen, 2021). Erbas & Maksuti elaborates that AI did not simply emerge out of nowhere, but the technology has been in existence for some time before it was seriously considered as a scientific field of study (Haroon-Sheikh, 2023).

From an administrative perspective, AI is increasingly used to streamline routine processes such as grading, enrollment, scheduling, and communication. Automated grading systems assesses objective-type questions with high accuracy and evaluate written responses through natural language processing (NLP), as these software applications reduce the workload of academic staff, allowing more time to focus on instructional planning and student engagement. In higher education, AI has also been applied in academic research and curriculum development, as AI-powered platforms assist researchers in literature reviews, data analysis, and plagiarism detection. While in curriculum design, machine learning algorithms are increasingly optimized to analyze labor market trends to inform course offerings in concurrence with market/industry demands.

This study is anchored upon two key theoretical models, namely, the Socio-Technical Systems Theory (STS) and the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). These theories provide a robust framework for analyzing the impact of AI on digital educational management, as STS theory emphasizes the need for a systems-based approach that considers both technological and human dimensions, TAM provides insight into the behavioral intentions and attitudes of users. This dual-theoretical perspective enables the study to assess not only the functional impact of AI tools but also the socio-cultural and psychological factors that mediate their effectiveness in the Nigerian educational context.

Statement of the Problem

Despite the growing integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) into various aspects of education, there remains limited empirical understanding of how these technologies are being adopted and utilized within different educational contexts. While AI applications such as intelligent tutoring, automated grading systems, and data analyses offer potential benefits in enhancing learning and administrative efficiency, their implementation raises questions regarding accessibility, effectiveness, and alignment with pedagogical objectives. Akinwalere & Ivanov (2022) lamented that the complexity of human intelligence had been long underestimated as technological limitations and managerial challenges remain in the development of expert systems, inhibiting the use of artificial intelligence in higher education and alongside its perils, despite the best intentions of those who develop and use these systems, thereby instigating negative unintended consequences, as disparities in technological infrastructure, institutional capacity, and policy development contribute to its uneven adoption across regions and school systems. It therefore becomes necessary to investigate the practical implications, challenges, and outcomes associated with their use, as a clearer understanding is required to inform evidence-based decisions and ensure that AI integration supports meaningful educational progress without compromising ethical, social,

or instructional standards. In Nigeria, the educational systems are facing persistent challenges related to administrative inefficiencies, data mismanagement, limited transparency, and resource allocation constraints (Ekwevugbe & Atare, 2024; Ekwevugbe & Atare, 2022; Ekwevugbe, 2014)

These issues are especially pronounced in public institutions, where outdated manual processes and inadequate digital infrastructure hinder effective planning, monitoring, and decision-making. With the increasing complexity of managing large student populations, curriculum delivery, and administrative logistics, there is a pressing need for more innovative and data-driven approaches to school management. This gap in research and practice raises critical questions, as this study seeks to fill that gap by investigating the impact of AI technology on the digital management of educational systems in Nigeria. It focuses on identifying the types of AI tools being used, assessing their contributions to administrative and academic management, and understanding the challenges institutions face in adopting such technologies. This study therefore seeks to explore the impact of artificial intelligence technology on digital management of educational systems in Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study;

1. What types of Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools are currently being utilized in the administration and academic operations of educational institutions in Nigeria?
2. In what ways do AI tools contribute to enhancing administrative efficiency and academic management within these institutions?
3. To what extent have AI technologies been integrated into the digital management systems of educational institutions in Nigeria?
4. What is the perceived impact of AI adoption on administrative processes, decision-making, and the overall effectiveness of institutional operations?
5. What are the major challenges and barriers affecting the adoption, implementation, and long-term sustainability of AI technologies in Nigerian educational institutions?

Research Hypotheses

1. There is no significant relationship between the types of AI tools used and the functional areas (administrative or academic) in which they are applied in Nigerian educational institutions.
2. AI tools do not contribute significantly to improvements in administrative efficiency and academic management in educational institutions.
3. The level of AI integration is not significantly associated with the degree of digital transformation in the management of educational institutions in Nigeria.
4. The adoption of AI technologies has a negative impact on administrative decision-making and overall institutional effectiveness.
5. Challenges such as inadequate infrastructure, limited technical expertise, and lack of policy support significantly hinder the adoption and sustainability of AI technologies in Nigerian educational institutions.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopts a descriptive survey research design using population of three public and two private universities in Delta State, Nigeria, within the context of the 2023/2024 academic session. Lecturers and students from the various Universities were targeted as the respondents for this study.

Random sampling technique was used to select three hundred and eighty (380) lecturers and students made up of twenty (20) lecturers and fifty six (56) students per university.

The instrument used in this study is a self-structured questionnaire consisting of three (3) sections, with section 1 covering demographic variables, while section 2 and 3 outlined the dependent and independent variables, using the test-retest with a Pearson's product correlation coefficient value of 0.78 the reliability of the instrument was assured, while analysis was done with descriptive statistics and t-test statistics.

RESULTS

Research Question One: *What types of Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools are currently being utilized in the administration and academic operations of educational institutions in Nigeria?*

Table 1: Mean score of the types of Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools are currently being utilized in the administration and academic operations of educational institutions in Nigeria

S/No	Independent Variable Items	N	SA	A	SD	D	Mean
Perceived use or availability of different AI tools							
1	AI-powered grading systems are used to assess student assignments in this institution.	380	9	35	176	160	1.718
2	Chatbots or virtual assistants are used to respond to student or staff inquiries	380	50	80	120	130	2.132
3	Predictive analytics tools are used to monitor and evaluate student performance.	380	92	70	85	133	2.318
4	Intelligent scheduling systems are used to automate timetables or course allocations.	380	58	65	139	118	2.166
5	This institution uses AI tools to support personalized learning experiences.	380	96	110	75	99	2.534
Group Mean							2.174
Dependent Variable Items							
Observed impact on administration and academic operations							
6	The use of AI tools has improved the efficiency of administrative tasks in this institution.	380	118	126	73	63	2.787
7	AI technologies have contributed to better decision-making in academic planning.	380	115	90	80	95	2.592
8	The adoption of AI tools has enhanced communication between staff and students.	380	146	91	63	80	2.797
9	AI systems have reduced the workload for academic and administrative staff.	380	139	101	79	61	2.837
10	The use of AI has led to measurable improvements in academic service delivery.	380	121	133	55	71	2.800
Group Mean							2.763
Total Mean							2.468

Key: 0.1-1.25 = Strongly Disagree, 1.26 – 2.4 = Disagree, 2.5 – 3.75 = Agree, 3.76 – 4.00 = Strongly Agree

The table displays all variable items regarding the types of Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools that are currently being utilized in the administration and academic operations of educational institutions in Nigeria had a mean scores of 2.468 that is below the average mean mark of 2.50, and falling within the 1.26 – 2.4 = Disagree category., indicating thereby that respondent’s disagree that all the above variables raised were the types of Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools currently being utilized in the administration and academic operations of educational institutions in Nigeria. Specifically they highlighted that AI-powered grading systems were not being used to assess student assignments, Chatbots or virtual assistants were not

being used to respond to student or staff inquiries, Predictive analytics tools were not being used to monitor and evaluate student performance, and Intelligent scheduling systems were not used to automate timetables or course allocations. They however opted that their institution uses AI tools to support personalized learning experiences having an individual mean of 2.534 but with an overall group mean of 2.174 that is below the mean benchmark. AI systems have reduced the workload for academic and administrative staff and the use of AI has led to measurable improvements in academic service delivery, with all individual mean score higher than the average mean and with a group mean of 2.63 also above the mean benchmark. Conclusively, the findings indicate limited adoption of specific AI tools exist while attesting that AI has contributed to improved administrative efficiency in Nigerian educational institutions.

Research Question Two: *In what ways do AI tools contribute to enhancing administrative efficiency and academic management within these institutions?*

Table 2: Mean score of ways in which AI tools contribute to enhancing administrative efficiency and academic management within these institutions

S/No	Independent Variable Items	N	SA	A	SD	D	Mean
Extent and nature of AI tool usage							
1	This institution uses AI tools to automate routine administrative tasks such as admissions and record-keeping.	380	110	120	80	70	2.737
2	AI technologies are used to generate performance reports for staff and students.	380	138	71	125	46	2.616
3	AI-based decision support systems are employed in strategic planning and resource allocation.	380	65	47	129	139	2.053
4	Academic advising and course registration processes are supported by AI systems.	380	77	50	112	141	2.095
5	This institution has adopted AI-enabled tools for managing digital academic records and documentation	380	148	75	96	61	2.624
Group mean							2.425
Dependent Variable Items							
Perceived contributions of AI to administrative efficiency and academic management							
6	AI tools have improved the speed and accuracy of administrative operations in this institution.	380	136	85	60	99	2.679
7	The use of AI has helped reduce human errors in academic data processing and reporting.	382	145	129	44	64	2.945
8	AI systems have enhanced coordination and planning among academic departments.	380	102	88	92	98	2.511
9	There is greater transparency and accountability in academic management due to AI integration.	380	161	120	35	64	2.995
10	AI technologies have contributed to more timely and effective administrative decision-making.	380	119	136	91	34	2.895
Group mean							2.805
Total Mean							2.615

Key: 0.1-1.25 = Strongly Disagree, 1.26 – 2.4 = Disagree, 2.5 – 3.75 = Agree, 3.76 – 4.00 = Strongly Agree

Table 2 reveals that there is greater transparency and accountability in academic management due to AI integration and AI technologies have contributed to more timely and effective administrative decision-making, based on the fact that their individual means were above the average mean mark of 2.50 with a group mean of 2.805.

Research Question Three: *To what extent have AI technologies been integrated into the digital management systems of educational institutions in Nigeria?*

Table 3: Mean score on the extent to which AI technologies been integrated into the digital management systems of educational institutions in Nigeria

S/No	Independent Variable Items	N	GE	AE	LE	NE	Mean
Level of AI technology integration							
1	AI technologies are actively integrated into the student information management system.	380	60	55	120	145	2.079
2	This institution uses AI tools for managing human resources and staff records.	380	59	72	148	101	2.234
3	AI-based platforms are used to monitor and evaluate institutional performance metrics.	380	39	66	120	155	1.971
4	The financial management system of the institution incorporates AI for planning and forecasting.	380	31	33	128	188	1.755
5	There is a structured policy supporting the integration of AI tools in digital management processes.	380	18	21	79	262	1.461
Group Mean							1.900
Dependent Variable Items							
Impact on digital management effectiveness							
6	The integration of AI tools has enhanced the accuracy and consistency of digital records.	380	102	99	67	112	2.503
7	AI integration has improved the responsiveness and quality of administrative services.	380	144	108	74	54	2.900
8	AI-enabled systems have streamlined workflow and reduced operational delays.	380	166	88	32	94	2.858
9	There is noticeable improvement in data-driven decision-making as a result of AI integration.	380	172	94	44	70	2.968
10	The institution's digital management systems have become more efficient and user-friendly due to AI.	380	126	140	30	84	2.811
Group Mean							2.808
Total Mean							2.354

Key: 0.1-1.25 = No Extent, 1.26 – 2.4 = Low Extent, 2.5 – 3.75 = Average Extent, 3.76 – 4.00 = Great Extent

The table (3) displays variables item on the extent to which AI technologies have been integrated into the digital management systems of educational institutions in Nigeria, showing that AI technologies were not actively integrated into the student information management system, this is so because their individual mean scores are below the average mean bench mark and the group mean of 1.900 also below the average mean bench mark. However the total mean score of 2.354 shows that AI technologies been integrated into the digital management systems of educational institutions in Nigeria to a low extent.

Research Question Four: *What is the perceived impact of AI adoption on administrative processes, decision-making, and the overall effectiveness of institutional operations?*

Table 4: Mean score of the perceived impact of AI adoption on administrative processes, decision-making, and the overall effectiveness of institutional operations

S/No	Independent Variable Items	N	SA	A	SD	D	Mean
Level of AI adoption in various institutional processes							
1	AI technologies have been adopted for automating routine administrative tasks (e.g., admissions, scheduling).	380	74	53	138	115	2.171
2	The institution uses AI-powered tools for collecting and analyzing performance data.	380	43	22	175	140	1.861
3	AI applications support decision-making in areas such as resource allocation and academic planning.	380	60	46	134	140	2.032
4	There are clear institutional strategies or policies guiding the implementation of AI tools.	380	43	122	77	138	2.392
5	Staff and administrators receive adequate training on the use of AI technologies in their roles.	380	87	66	171	56	2.429
Group mean							2.177
Dependent Variable Items							
Perceived impact on administrative processes, decision-making, and institutional effectiveness							
6	AI tools have improved the accuracy and speed of administrative processes.	380	128	84	77	91	2.655
7	The use of AI has enhanced the quality of decisions made by institutional leaders.	380	174	130	23	53	3.118
8	AI-driven systems have made institutional operations more transparent and accountable.	380	129	73	80	98	2.613
9	Overall, AI adoption has contributed to more efficient and responsive institutional management.	380	162	120	47	51	3.034
10	The institution is perceived to be more effective in achieving its goals since the integration of AI.	380	133	150	55	42	2.984
Group mean							2.881
Total Mean							2.529

Key: 0.1-1.25 = Strongly Disagree, 1.26 – 2.4 = Disagree, 2.5 – 3.75 = Agree, 3.76 – 4.00 = Strongly Agree

The table (4) reveals on one hand, the perceived impact of AI adoption on administrative processes, decision-making, and the overall effectiveness of institutional operations, by AI technologies not being adopted for automating routine administrative tasks (e.g., admissions, scheduling), not using AI-powered tools for collecting and analyzing performance data, AI applications not supporting decision-making in areas such as resource allocation and academic planning, with no clear institutional strategies or policies guiding the implementation of AI tools, while Staff and administrators do not receive adequate training on the use of AI technologies in their roles as a result of the fact that their individual mean scores were below the average mean bench mark with a group mean of 2.177 also below the benchmark average mean of 2.50.

On the other hand, the table revealed that AI tools have improved the accuracy and speed of administrative processes. The use of AI has enhanced the quality of decisions made by institutional leaders; AI-driven systems have made institutional operations more transparent and accountable.

Research Question Five: *What are the major challenges and barriers affecting the adoption, implementation, and long-term sustainability of AI technologies in Nigerian educational institutions?*

Table 5: Mean score of the major challenges and barriers affecting the adoption, implementation, and long-term sustainability of AI technologies in Nigerian educational institutions

S/No	Independent Variable Items	N	SA	A	SD	D	Mean
Challenges and barriers to AI adoption and sustainability							
1	Lack of adequate funding limits the adoption of AI technologies in my institution	380	153	125	40	62	2.897
2	There is insufficient technical infrastructure (e.g., internet, hardware, software) to support AI implementation	380	80	65	120	115	2.250
3	Limited digital skills among staff and administrators hinder effective use of AI tools	380	141	154	53	32	3.097
4	There is a lack of clear policy or strategic framework for AI integration in the institution	380	132	148	67	33	3.039
5	Resistance to change among staff and leadership is a significant barrier to AI adoption	380	180	76	78	46	2.753
Group mean							2.807
Dependent Variable Items							
Impact of challenges on implementation and sustainability							
6	The challenges faced have slowed down the implementation of AI technologies in this institution	380	138	84	59	99	2.687
7	Due to existing barriers, the full potential of AI to improve educational operations is not being realized	380	176	139	22	43	3.179
8	Sustainability of AI initiatives is threatened by the absence of long-term planning and investment	380	129	93	70	88	2.692
9	Frequent technical issues or downtime hinder the consistent use of AI tools	380	168	124	37	51	3.076
10	The institutional effectiveness of AI systems is negatively affected by these ongoing barriers	380	124	132	70	54	2.858
Group mean							2.898
Total Mean							2.853

Key: 0.1-1.25 = Strongly Disagree, 1.26 – 2.4 = Disagree, 2.5 – 3.75 = Agree, 3.76 – 4.00 = Strongly Agree

The table (5) reveals all variable items with regards to the major challenges and barriers affecting the adoption, implementation, and long-term sustainability of AI technologies in Nigerian educational institutions showing that Lack of adequate funding limits the adoption of AI technologies in my institution, insufficient technical infrastructure (e.g., internet, hardware, software) to support AI implementation, Limited digital skills among staff and administrators hinder effective use of AI tools, a lack of clear policy or strategic framework for AI integration in the institution and Resistance to change among staff and leadership is a significant barrier to AI adoption having their mean above the average mean bench mark and a group mean of 2.807 also above the average mean mark of 2.50.

Research Hypotheses

Hypothesis One:

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between the types of AI tools used and the functional areas (administrative or academic) in which they are applied in Nigerian educational institutions

Table 6 one tailed t-test table on significant relationship between the types of AI tools used and the functional areas (administrative or academic) in which they are applied in Nigerian educational institutions

Variables	N	Mean	SD	t-calc	t-crit	df	P	Decision
types of AI tools used	5	2.174	0.268	4.674	1.860	8	0.002	Reject Null
the functional areas (administrative or academic) in which they are applied in Nigerian educational institutions	5	2.763	0.087					

Table 6 present the results of a t-test analyzing the relationship between the types of AI tools used and their application in different functional areas (administrative or academic) within Nigerian educational institutions. The analysis yielded a t-calculated value of 4.674, which is significantly higher than the critical t-value of 1.860, and a p-value of 0.0016, indicating strong statistical significance. As a result, the null hypothesis is rejected, and the alternate hypothesis is accepted, confirming that there is a significant relationship between the types of AI tools adopted and the specific functional areas in which they are applied.

Hypothesis Two:

H02: AI tools do not contribute significantly to improvements in administrative efficiency and academic management in educational institutions.

Table 7 two tailed t-test table on contribution of Ai tools contribute to improvements in administrative efficiency and academic management in educational institutions.

Variables	N	Mean	SD	t-calc	t-crit	df	P	Decision
Ai tools	5	2.425	0.290	2.482	1.860	8	0.038	Reject Null
contribution to improvements in administrative efficiency and academic management in educational institutions	5	2.805	0.182					

Table 7 shows the results of a t-test analyzing the relationship between Ai tools and its contributing to improvements in administrative efficiency and academic management in educational institutions. The analysis yielded a t-calculated value of 2.482, which is significantly higher than the critical t-value of

1.860, and a p-value of 0.038, indicating strong statistical significance, resulting in the null hypothesis is rejected, and the alternate hypothesis is accepted, confirming that AI tools contribute significantly to improvements in administrative efficiency and academic management in educational institutions.

Hypothesis Three: Ho3: The level of AI integration is not significantly associated with the degree of digital transformation in the management of educational institutions in Nigeria.

Table 8 one tailed t-test on the level of AI integration and the degree of digital transformation in the management of educational institutions in Nigeria

Variables	N	Mean	SD	t-calc	t-crit	df	P	Decision
The level of AI integration	5	1.900	0.269	6.476	1.860	8	0.0002	Reject Null
the degree of digital transformation in the management of educational institutions in Nigeria	5	2.808	0.161					

Table 8 show a t-test measuring the mean values for the variables between the level of AI integration and the degree of digital transformation in the management of educational institutions in Nigeria. The table revealed an absolute t-calculated value of 6.476 significantly higher than the standard t-critical or table value of 1.860, with a p value of 0.0002, highlighting that the null hypothesis be rejected, while accepting the alternate hypothesis stating that The level of AI integration is significantly associated with the degree of digital transformation in the management of educational institutions in Nigeria.

Hypothesis Four:

Ho4: The adoption of AI technologies has a negative impact on administrative decision-making and overall institutional effectiveness.

Table 9 one tailed t-test table on the adoption of AI technologies and impact on administrative decision-making and overall institutional effectiveness

Variables	N	Mean	SD	t-calc	t-crit	df	P	Decision
the adoption of AI technologies	5	2.177	0.240	4.736	1.860	8	0.0015	Reject Null
impact on administrative decision-making and overall institutional effectiveness	5	2.881	0.230					

Table 9 shows the results of a t-test analyzing the relationship between AI technologies and impact on administrative decision-making and overall institutional effectiveness. The analysis yielded a t-calculated value of 4.736, which is significantly higher than the critical t-value of 1.860, and a p-value of 0.0015, indicating strong statistical significance, resulting in the null hypothesis is rejected, and the alternate hypothesis is accepted, confirming that the adoption of AI technologies has a positive impact on administrative decision-making and overall institutional effectiveness.

Hypothesis Five:

Ho5: Challenges such as inadequate infrastructure, limited technical expertise, and lack of policy support do not significantly hinder the adoption and sustainability of AI technologies in Nigerian educational institutions.

Table 10 one tailed t-test table on challenges facing the adoption and sustainability of AI technologies in Nigerian educational institutions

Variables	N	Mean	SD	t-calc	t-crit	df	P	Decision
challenges such as inadequate infrastructure, limited technical expertise, and lack of policy support	5	2.807	0.339	0.5015	1.860	8	0.630	Accept Null
the adoption and sustainability of AI technologies in Nigerian educational institutions	5	2.898	0.223					

Table 10 shows the results of a t-test analyzing the relationship between challenges such as inadequate infrastructure, limited technical expertise, and lack of policy support and the adoption and sustainability of AI technologies in Nigerian educational institutions. The analysis yielded a t-calculated value of 0.5015, which is significantly lower than the critical t-value of 1.860, and a p-value of 0.630, indicating no statistical significance, resulting in the null hypothesis being accepted, affirming that challenges such as inadequate infrastructure, limited technical expertise, and lack of policy support significantly hinder the adoption and sustainability of AI technologies in Nigerian educational institutions.

DISCUSSION

The findings indicates limited adoption of specific AI tools such as grading systems, chatbots, predictive analytics, and scheduling software in Nigerian educational institutions however, there is evidence that AI is making a positive impact in other areas. Notably, AI has contributed to improved administrative efficiency, enhanced academic planning and better communication, reduced staff workload, as confirmed by Mahendra (2023). This suggests that although the integration of AI in core academic functions remains low, its growing application in administrative processes reflects a gradual shift toward embracing AI technologies in the education sector.

The findings further shows a mixed perception of AI integration in Nigerian educational institutions, while disagreeing with the use of AI in strategic planning, resource allocation, academic advising, and course registration, at the same time acknowledging the significant role AI plays in enhancing administrative efficiency, as this is in line with Pedro et al. (2019); Grosz & Stone, (2018) & Mohammed & Watson, (2019). Specifically, AI was reported to improve routine tasks such as admissions, record-keeping, performance reporting, and digital documentation. Overall, the findings suggest a generally positive outlook on AI's impact on administrative and academic management, despite some areas of limited application.

The findings further indicate that AI technologies have been integrated into the digital management systems of educational institutions in Nigeria to a low extent, as AI are not actively used in core digital management areas such as student information systems, human resources, institutional performance monitoring, financial planning, and policy support. However, there is acknowledgment of the benefits where AI has been applied, with positive responses highlighting improved accuracy of digital records, enhanced administrative service quality, streamlined workflows, better data-driven decision-making, and

more efficient, user-friendly systems. This suggests that while integration remains limited, the potential impact of AI on digital management is recognized and valued.

The findings also shows that while respondents indicated limited adoption of AI for routine administrative tasks, data analysis, strategic decision-making, and staff training they also recognized significant benefits where AI has been implemented. These benefits include improved accuracy and speed of processes, enhanced decision-making quality, greater transparency and accountability, and more efficient and responsive institutional management. The finding also shows that Nigerian educational institutions face significant challenges in adopting, implementing, and sustaining AI technologies. Similar to the findings of Haroon-Sheikh (2023)

It was further revealed that a statistically significant relationship exist between the types of AI tools used and their application in either administrative or academic functions in Nigerian educational institutions, indicating that AI adoption is function-specific rather than uniformly applied across all areas. The findings further indicate that a statistically significant relationship does exist between the use of AI tools and improvements in administrative efficiency and academic management in educational institutions, confirming that AI tools play a meaningful role in enhancing institutional operations. The findings also demonstrate that a statistically significant relationship exists between the level of AI integration and the degree of digital transformation in the management of educational institutions in Nigeria, confirming that higher levels of AI integration are strongly associated with greater digital transformation in institutional management.

The findings further confirm that a statistically significant relationship does exist between the adoption of AI technologies and their impact on administrative decision-making and overall institutional effectiveness.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the findings reveal a complex but progressively positive landscape for AI adoption in Nigerian educational institutions. While the use of specific AI tools in core academic functions such as grading, advising, and scheduling remains limited, AI is making a notable impact in administrative areas by improving efficiency, decision-making, communication, and service delivery. There is a growing recognition of AI's value in streamlining operations, enhancing transparency, and supporting data-driven management, despite persistent challenges such as inadequate infrastructure, limited technical expertise, and lack of strategic policy frameworks. Statistically significant relationships confirm that AI adoption varies by functional area and is positively linked to improvements in administrative performance, digital transformation, and institutional effectiveness. However, widespread integration is still hindered by real and significant barriers that must be addressed for the full benefits of AI to be realized across the education sector in Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The study therefore provides actionable recommendations as follows;

1. Educational institutions and policymakers should establish clear frameworks and guidelines to support the structured adoption and use of AI across academic and administrative functions.
2. Increased funding and investment are needed to improve internet connectivity, hardware, and software systems that support AI implementation.
3. Regular training programs should be organized to enhance the digital skills of staff and administrators, ensuring effective use and management of AI technologies.
4. Institutions should expand the use of AI tools beyond administrative tasks to include academic functions such as grading, advising, and performance analytics.
5. Efforts should be made to overcome resistance to change, reduce technical disruptions, and ensure long-term planning for sustainable AI adoption in the education sector.

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